

"THE IMPORTANCE OF COLOR HARMONY IN FINE ARTS"

Kadirova Nodirakhon Anvarjon qizi

Teacher of school No. 49 of Uchkuprik district of Fergana region

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6726882>

Annotation

The scientific basis of painting is the science of color science. Coloring teaches future artists how to create and distribute colors in nature, how they change under the influence of the environment, how to prepare and use paints, and in this article the art of painting. information about

Keywords: Color, saturation, chromatic and achromatic colors, Painting.

In Central Asia, the doctrine of color has long been associated with book miniatures, painting, frescoes, and panels. Because the art of painting requires the ability to choose colors and prepare them. Therefore, every student should first of all learn the secrets of color preparation and the chemical processes involved in this work.

Scientists and artists have long been interested in how colors are formed and distributed in nature. The great Renaissance painters and theorists Mon Batista Alberti, Leonardo da Vinci, and others wrote about the properties of color in their paintings.

Color plays an important role in human life. It affects a person differently in different situations. So it is no coincidence that we sometimes call colors "hira" which can mean "happy" and depressing. It is well-known that from ancient times people have used color in their work, taking into account these properties. Especially as such a tool, artists have skillfully used it. They have been able to create thought-provoking images by painting their works in different colors and influencing people's moods in different ways. Therefore, in many genres of fine art, both color and the ability to use it are very important. But it is also true that the power of the pen is important and powerful. Therefore, from ancient times the view of working in pencil drawing was formed as the basis of painting. But a good understanding of color is important for any learner of drawing.

Our lives are full of colors. We see our surroundings, the whole world in color. We are so accustomed to blue skies, green meadows, red, yellow, white, and black cars that we forget that color is actually a subjective interpretation of electromagnetic radiation in the optical range. Color is the wave of light that our eyes perceive, and we see it differently depending on its length. The word "color" is known to be derived from Persian. In addition, many colors have Persian names: "blue", "purple", "pink", "red", "brown", "pink", "black", "blue"

(Arabic core); Although the first component of "gray" is the root word "gray", the compound structure suggests that it appeared in later times, under the influence of Persian culture.

The colors are also light red, ie bright red, orange. dark red, light yellow, and saturated, that is, bright, dull. Colors that are opposite in the color range are called "contrast" colors. Contrasting colors contrast sharply, making one brighter than the other. For example, red appears brighter on a green background, and green appears brighter on a red background. When working with color, it is important to know the harmony of colors, that is, the harmony of colors.

Watercolors, tempera, watercolors, and gouache are used to describe objects and events. Painting is a complex process that requires a person to know the properties of colors and how to use them effectively and intelligently. The use of paints to describe the size, texture, and spatial condition of an object is the basis of painting. As long as the images that draw everything, he should pay serious attention to the colors. That's when you realize that color is different in nature. Because the color of an object changes depending on how close it is to us. This is because the weather affects the appearance of the object. Finding and using the right proportions of colors at the paper level is one of the most important factors in the true reflection of a painting. Working with watercolors is a job that requires a lot of study and practice. The theoretical part of the work requires careful study at the same time as practice. All colors except chromatic colors, that is, colors that have a hue, are included in chromatic colors. It includes all the colors of the solar spectrum and all the colors that come from mixing them with each other. White is also a chromatic color.

Chromatic colors, unlike achromatic colors, differ not only in the power of light, but also in their names and colors. For example, yellow differs sharply from red in both the intensity of its light and its color. Each chromatic color has three properties. They have hue, brightness (which means more or less brightness), and color saturation (which means more or less brightness in the fall). Each chromatic color differs from each other by these three properties.

From the above, it is clear that chromatic colors differ from each other in three main properties - color tone (color itself), color brightness and saturation. If we look closely at the spectrum, we can see the similarities between the red and purple colors at the very edges. When the two colors are combined, red is formed between them. The ring is formed when the spectrum is connected by placing the resulting color between red and purple. This is called the range of

colors in color science. The colors range from red, orange, yellow, yellow, green, green, blue, blue, blue, purple, and red.

There can be many shades of color. But our eyes can distinguish about 150 of them. The order in which the colors are arranged in a circle is preserved. If the color scheme is divided into two equal parts, the first half will be red, orange, yellow-green (pistachio), and the second half will be green-blue, turquoise, blue, blue-purple. The first half of the circle is warm colors and the second half is cool colors. The reason for this is that the colors red and yellow are reminiscent of fire, hot iron is reminiscent of coal, and blue, blue and green are reminiscent of ice and water. This difference is relative, and any warm color may appear cold next to a warmer color, and conversely, a cold color may appear warmer than a colder color.

Chemistry helps to find dyes, chemically add substances, and determine the recipes of dyes. Dyes are prepared in two main ways. The names of the paints are often distinguished by the name of the place where they were excavated.

Take, for example, the Neopolitan yellow dye, which is made from a volcanic eruption in the mountains around the Italian city of Naples. Khalilovka ocher is a golden dye obtained from the village of Khalilovka in the Orenburg region of the Urals. Indian yellow is an orange dye made from the leaves of a palm tree that grows in the Indian state of Bengal. Some bright red dyes are made from small animals such as the oak beetle (2-8 mm in size) and the red worm from North America.

The color is determined by the wavelength of the colors. According to this property of color, we see and perceive red, yellow, blue and other spectral colors through the eyes. But there are more colors than just the color names. The wavelength of the color does not change. Because when white is added, only the brightness of the color changes and is expressed by the reflection coefficient. A device called a photometer is used to accurately measure brightness.

Painting. Painting is one of the types of fine arts that reflect the real life and influence the thoughts and feelings of the audience.

A work of art on a surface made of paints (watercolor, tempera, watercolor, gouache, etc.) is called a painting. The images in the painting are very bright and spectacular. Artists create their works with paintings and plastic tools. Although they use the features of pencil and composition, one of the main tools for painting is color.

Images in the painting are created using paints that form a continuous layer of paint on the image level. Even in watercolor painting, even if there are

untouched areas on the paper, it does not affect the continuity of the image, because the paints absorb and mix with each other.

The pictorial and expressive potential of color is used in painting with the freedom and full power necessary for the artist. Color can be used to highlight the main idea of the composition, to highlight important details, to give the depth of the distance, or to give the image flatness.

The most important distinguishing features of painting are that in it the image of shape and distance, images and movements are seen only through color.

Painting reflects the complex world of human emotions and character, as well as the subtle changes of nature, the delivery of fantastic images and philosophical ideas. All this is given through the genres of painting.

The diversity of objects, events and happenings in the world and the growing interest of artists in them led to the emergence of various regional genres in painting in the XVII century. These were portraits, landscapes, still lifes, animalistic, legendary, historical, superstitious and everyday genres. Genres or their elements may interfere in a painting. For example, a still life and a landscape can successfully complement a portrait.

Использованная литература:

1. Ortiqboy, S. S., & Makhsudali, J. (2022). A Desire Sung in a Pattern. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF ARTS AND DESIGN, 3(5), 6-9.
2. Prozorova, M. N., Zharkov, A. D., Zharkova, A. A., Khamdamova, V. A., Sattorova, S. O., & Losev, V. S. (2021). University graduate career potential in digital transformation period: Features and problems of formation. Linguistics and Culture Review, 5(S3), 1574-1585.
3. Sattorova, S. O. (2021). PATTERN SUNG ON THE CARPET. Экономика и социум, (5-1), 445-448.
4. Abdurahimovich, M. A., & Qizi, S. S. O. (2020). Master Student Etiquette. www.conferencepublication.com, 22.
5. Khaydarovich, A. A. (2020). Colors in Descriptive Art. International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development, 2(12), 20-22.
6. Mamadjananivich, B. B. IT is Necessary to Feed the World with Beauty!. International Journal on Integrated Education, 3(8), 215-217.
7. Sattorova Sarvinoz Ortiqboy qizi1 , Abdullayev Alimardon Khaydarovich, Sodikova Irodahon Gayratjon qizi INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ECONOMICS, FINANCE AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT ISSN (electronic): 2620-6269/ ISSN (printed): 2615-4021, <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/333575-colors-in-descriptive-art-8237ee5d.pdf>

8. Bulatov S.S. Color psychology. T., TDPU named after Nizami 2004.
9. Tursunaliev T.N. Glossary of color terms. –T. TDPU named after Nizami. 2002. -20 b.
10. Egamov H. Working with paints. -T .: Teacher, 1981. -56 p

